

Quantification of Stimulated Raman Scattering Penalties Induced by Very High Speed PON in Quadruple Coexistence

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Abstract: To determine the wavelength plan for VHSP, we study the penalties induced on legacy PONs through Raman scattering. The ~1300nm region seems the best tradeoff for IMDD-VHSP. Regarding S/C/L-bands, removing G-PON would relax the constraints. © 2024 The Authors

1. Introduction

International Telecommunication Union (ITU-T) recently released the physical media dependent specification related to the 50 Gigabit capable Passive Optical Network (50G-PON) and is currently evaluating solutions for its successor, the Very High Speed PON (VHSP). The latter should reach a line rates of 100/200 Gb/s, exploiting either Intensity Modulation and Direct Detection (IMDD) with one or several wavelength pairs, or a flavour of coherent transmission [1]. In both cases, high optical launch powers are expected since important optical budget class must be met (such as class D, 20-35 dB, to meet 1:128 split ratio or higher) and since affordable receivers' sensitivity comes to their limits. Recent research works on IMDD transmissions for VHSP assumed powers as high as 16 dBm or even 20.5 dBm per wavelength to meet the strong PON Optical Path Loss (OPL) requirements [2], [3]. Such high launch optical power would trigger non-linear effects, even more if several IMDD channels are needed and add up. Regarding the coherent option, the very nature of data transmission using optical phase modulation makes it sensitive to Self-Phase Modulation (SPM). Beyond a threshold about 13 to 15 dBm the OPL performance is not improved [4], [5]. Stimulated Brillouin scattering was also studied in IMDD context and can easily be mitigated [3], [6]. Eye safety is ensured in that range since the power limits for class 1M is 24.4 dBm in O-band and 21.3 dBm in C-band [7].

The success of PON technologies comes partially from its ability to enable the coexistence of new (VHSP) and legacy PON technologies (GPON, XGSPON, 50GPON), in exploiting a proper wavelength plan, thus enabling smooth migrations, and sharing the infrastructure among four technologies [8]. The high launch power of VHSP might trigger non-linear effects which will affect legacy PON technologies through Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS). The latter is an inelastic phenomenon inducing a transfer of energy from a signal to another having a higher wavelength. The effect is maximized when the frequency shift between the signals is about 13.2 THz ($\Delta\lambda \sim 100$ nm) in Standard Single Mode Fiber (SSMF). While SRS is usually exploited in Raman amplification, in the context of PON it can induce a depletion of the received power of a legacy channel, and thus Optical Path Penalties (OPPs) and outages. In this work, we quantify the SRS interactions in a context where several PON technologies coexist, to discuss what should (or should not) be the VHSP wavelength plan.

2. Methodology

PON Optical Distribution Networks (ODNs) usually use a tree topology. The SRS will be negligible in the "branches" of the ODN since the optical splitter will limit the downstream (DS) signals' power. SRS can be induced in the branches by high upstream (US) power, but SRS is also very dependent to the fiber length, and PON tree branches are usually shorter than the trunk on the field. Then, SRS would appear in the "trunk" of the ODN, because the VHSP-DS power is expected to be high (13-20 dBm). While US signals will be attenuated by the combiner's losses, it can be shown [9] that SRS requires only a strong signal to appear (VHSP-DS here), independently from the US signals power. For those reason, we will focus on the wavelength of VHSP-DS (referred as λ_{VHSP}).

$$\left\{ \pm \frac{dP_n}{dz} = -\alpha_n P_n - \sum_{p>n} \left[\frac{g_r(\lambda_n, \lambda_p)}{A_{eff}} \cdot \rho_{n,p}(z) \cdot \frac{\lambda_p}{\lambda_n} \cdot P_p \cdot P_n \right] + \sum_{n>p} \left[\frac{g_r(\lambda_p, \lambda_n)}{A_{eff}} \cdot \rho_{n,p}(z) \cdot P_p \cdot P_n \right] \right. \quad 1 \leq n \leq 7 \quad (1)$$

The model used here is described in [9] and exploits experimental data from our previous works [10]. It consists in a system of seven ordinary differential equations (a pair for each legacy PON, and one for VHSP-DS) summarized by Eq. 1, describing the evolution of the power $P(z)$ along the fiber. The first term on the right side ($\alpha_n P_n$) corresponds to the attenuation (which follows the general attenuation profile of SSMF), and the sign on the left side term corresponds to the propagation direction. The second term on the right side ($\sum_{p>n}$) corresponds to the depletion induced by SRS when channels with a higher wavelength which "suck up" energy from the considered channel. Similarly, the third term on the right side ($\sum_{n>p}$) is energy gained from lower wavelength channels. When $n=p$, $g_r=0$ (no SRS).

Beside the importance of the launch power channels, the OPPs depends on the effective area A_{eff} of the mode and the Raman gain g_r . A_{eff} reduces with the wavelength, while g_r depends on the frequency shift between the two channels (maximum at 13.2 THz, see Fig. 1), and increases in the low wavelength bands. As a results, in similar condition (e.g.

frequency shift of 13.2 THz and similar launch powers), the SRS impact will be higher in O-band than in C-band since the ratio g_r/A_{eff} is roughly 1.7 times higher, see Fig. 2. The factor $\rho_{n,p}$ accounts for the polarization overlap of the two signals at position z ($0 \leq \rho_{n,p} \leq 1$) since SRS is polarization dependent. According to our experiments and to the literature, $\rho_{n,p}$ is averaged for reaches of several kilometres because of the polarization mode dispersion and group velocity dependence to wavelength, whether the signals are co- or contra-propagating [11], so we set $\rho_{n,p}(z)=0.5$.

Fig. 1. Raman gain $g_r(\lambda_i, \lambda_j)$ spectral shape (the maximum of g_r is given of Fig.2).

Fig. 2. g_r/A_{eff} vs. wavelength according to experimental measurements from [9], [10]

Table 1. Summary of wavelengths and launch powers used in simulations.

Techno.	Launch power (dBm)	Wavel. (nm)
GPON-DS	7	1490
GPON-US	< 0	1310
XGSPON-DS	8	1577
XGSPON-US	< 0	1270
50GPON-DS	14	1342
50GPON-US	< 0	1286
VHSP	varied	varied

The PON wavelength plan and launch power are summarized in Table 1. The DS powers correspond to the higher bound of the C+ OPL class, and the US powers are the expected power launched in the trunk of the ODN (assuming C+ class), after passing through the splitter and then considered below 0 dBm. The VHSP-DS wavelength is tuned during the simulations from 1200 nm to 1800 nm, even if the SSMF cutoff wavelength is 1260 nm. The propagation length is set to 20 km, corresponding to the maximum reach of PON (DD20), to maximize SRS impact.

3. Results and discussions

The first results are reported on Fig .3. Each curve represents the on-off gain (if positive) or on-off depletion (if negative) induced by the other channels, depending on the VHSP-DS wavelength when emitting 16 dBm. For example, for $\lambda_{VHSP}=1400$ nm, the GPON DS (red dotted line) benefit from 0.8 dB gain, mainly due to the presence of VHSP, since GPON DS's wavelength (1490 nm) is roughly 13 THz below. Alternatively, the effect is reversed when $\lambda_{VHSP}=1600$ nm: GPON-DS depletion is 0.85 dB because of VHSP. The extremities of the considered wavelength range show an "offset" which corresponds to the fact that the "legacy" PON technologies already induce SRS on each other even in the absence of VHSP-DS, or if the VHSP is too far, spectrally speaking, to induce SRS. For example, at $\lambda_{VHSP}=1800$ nm, the XGS-PON US (green dashed-dotted line) experiences 0.7 dB of depletion because of the presence of 50GPON-DS launched with 14 dBm, as we experimentally observed in [10].

Fig. 3. Depletion and gain of all PON technologies vs. VHSP's wavelength ($P_{VHSP} = 16$ dBm, $L=20$ km)

Fig. 4. Cumulative depletion of all PON technologies vs. VHSP wavelength for different VHSP launch powers

Fig. 5. Cumulative depletion of all PON technologies vs. VHSP wavelength when removing a legacy PON technology

To focus on the SRS induced only by VHSP deployment, the on-off depletion of all PON channels (including VHSP) are added, since a depletion means an optical penalty and a potential outage. The gain is not added since it may mask outages: for example, when $\lambda_{VHSP}=1400$ nm, GPON-DS (red dotted line) would experience about 0.8 dB gain, but GPON-US (red dash-dotted line) would suffer from 1.2 dB depletion, and only $0.8+(-1.2)=-0.4$ dB would be reported, hiding potential outages. As a result, to identify the SRS induced by VHSP introduction, only the depletions (i.e. the negative parts of the curves on Fig .3, minus the previously described offsets) are added together, as shows the orange curve on Fig .3.

Fig. 4 shows the cumulative depletion due to VHSP-DS obtained with the previously described process, but for different VHSP-DS launch power. The results show that, as expected, only the VHSP suffers from depletion induced by 50GPON-DS when its launch power is low (e.g. $P_{\text{VHSP}}=-20$ dBm). With more realistic P_{VHSP} launch powers, it appears that λ_{VHSP} should not be set in the 1310-1440 nm band since it will reinforce SRS depletion on O-band PON channels such as XGS-PON US, 50GPON US, or GPON US. With $\lambda_{\text{VHSP}}=1355$ nm, a cumulative depletion beyond 2.5 dB or even 5 dB could be reached with $P_{\text{VHSP}}=16$ dBm or $P_{\text{VHSP}}=19$ dBm, respectively. Unfortunately, the IMDD flavor of VHSP will have to get as close as possible to the minimum of SSMF chromatic dispersion (~ 1310 nm) because of the high baud rates expected. Regarding the coherent flavors of VHSP, S/C/L bands seem to be the preferred options since 1) it would re-use existing technologies (modulators, coherent receivers) 2) avoid non-linear effects such as SPM which are enhanced by the inverse of the effective area of the propagating mode (about $82 \mu\text{m}^2$ in C-band and $68 \mu\text{m}^2$ in O-band), and 3) since attenuation is limited and dispersion is easily compensated. Fig. 4 suggests avoiding the $\lambda_{\text{VHSP}}\sim 1600$ nm region to limit SRS induced depletion. The minimum of depletion is even achieved at $\lambda_{\text{VHSP}}=1490$ nm (0.3 dB depletion for $P_{\text{VHSP}}=19$ dBm), suggesting providing VHSP a wavelength range as close as possible to GPON DS (1490 ± 10 nm).

However, deploying VHSP may not require maintaining all legacy PON technologies, since there may be no need to have four PON generations coexisting at the same time, and since spectral resources are precious. We calculated the VHSP induced depletion with the same methodology as before but when one of the legacy PON technologies is removed, see Fig. 5, assuming $P_{\text{VHSP}}=16$ dBm. Compared to the previous case with all PON technologies (orange full line on Fig. 5), removing the GPON (red dashed curve) reduces the constraints in the S/C/L bands: the resulting cumulative OPPs are almost null in C-band. However, the depletion is not reduced below 1310 nm and remains higher than 1 dB in the O-band above 1310 nm. Getting rid of XGSPON instead of GPON (green dash-dotted curve) relaxes the constraints in the low O-band (about 0.5 dB cumulative depletion around 1300 nm) where standard wavelength channels could be exploited for VHSP, such as LAN-WDM (1269-1318 nm with 4 nm spacing), for single or multi-channel IMDD technologies. Also, a gap remains between the upper bound of 50GPON-US (1288 nm) and the lower bound of GPON-US (1300 nm, narrow option). The depletion remains similar in S/C/L bands than in the four coexisting PON scenario. Finally, removing 50GPON seems to be a possible option to maintain SRS penalties below 1.5 dB in O-band. In the ~ 1300 nm region, where the chromatic dispersion is low, the depletion even goes down to 0.25 dB. Regarding S/C/L bands, removing 50GPON would not have a major impact.

4. Conclusion

VHSP, either using coherent or intensity modulation, would involve high launch power and trigger nonlinear effects such as stimulated Raman scattering. Exploiting simulation models and experimental parameters, we provided estimations of the Raman scattering depletion due to VHSP introduction on legacy ITU-T technologies, in a scenario where several PON technologies coexist, assuming that those penalties would lead to loss of signals and outages. The results showed that for a launch power of 19 dBm and 20km of fiber, VHSP could induce beyond 5 dB of cumulative depletion on other PON channels if set to 1355 nm. The results suggest setting VHSP's wavelength as close as possible to GPON downstream (1490 nm) regarding the coherent option, or around 1300 nm if the power remains below 16 dBm, to limit the depletion to 0.75 dB in the IMDD option. If a single PON technology were to be removed, GPON would be the best candidate to limit the depletion impact in S/C/L band. Regarding O-band, removing the 50GPON (or reconsidering mass deployment, since it is at a trial stage at the time of writing) would limit SRS below 0.25 dB in the ~ 1300 nm region, while getting close enough to the null point of chromatic dispersion to enable high baud rate transmissions. Also, O-band standard channels or remaining "gap bands" could be reused.

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